

ILMIY-TEKNIKA JURNALI

 Farg'ona
Politexnika
Instituti

Scientific - technical journal

Научно-технический журнал
Ферганского
политехнического
института

2022. СПЕЦ. ВЫПУСК № 11

ISSN 2181-7200

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА
МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ

ФАРҒОНА ПОЛИТЕХНИКА ИНСТИТУТИ

И Л М И Й – Т Е Х Н И К А Ж У Р Н А Л И

2022. СПЕЦ. ВЫПУСК № 11

*НАУЧНО–ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ
ЖУРНАЛ ФерПИ*

*SCIENTIFIC –TECHNICAL
JOURNAL of FerPI*

ФАРҒОНА – 2022

ФарПИ ИЛМИЙ-ТЕХНИКА ЖУРНАЛИ ТАҲРИРИЯТИ

1997 йилдан буён нашр этилади.
Йилига 6 марта чоп қилинади.

ЎзР Олий аттестация комиссияси
Раёсатининг 2013 йил 30 декабрдаги
№201/3 қарори билан журнал ОАК нинг
илмий нашрлари рўйхатига киритилган

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Издаётся с 1997 года.
Выходит 6 раз в год.

Постановлением Президиума Высшей
аттестационной комиссии РУз №201/3
от 30 декабря 2013 г. журнал включен в
список научных изданий ВАК.

Главный редактор

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SCIENTIFIC – TECHNICAL JOURNAL of FerPI

It has been published since 1997.
It is printed 6 times a year.

The decision of Presidium of the Supreme
Attestation Committee of the RUz №201/3
from December, 30th, 2013 Journal is included
in the list of scientific editions of the SAC.

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Shunday ekan, alloma qoldirgan boy ilmiy-ma'naviy merosni ko'z qorachig'idek avaylab asrash va uni o'rganish har birimizda tarixga hurmat, undan g'ururlanish, avlod-ajdodlarimizga mehr-muhabbat tuyg'ularini shakllantirish bilan birga o'zligimizni anglash, ertangi kunga nisbatan ishonch tuyg'ularini mustahkamlaydi[4;68]. Zotan, bunday buyuk allomalarimizga munosib vorislar bo'lish tuyg'usi ana shunga undaydi.

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[Doi: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7344700](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7344700)

УДК 004:339.9.012.421

DIGITAL ECONOMY AS A FACTOR OF ACTIVATION OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

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(Received on November 5th, 2022)

The concept of the digital economy has gained popularity in recent years and has attracted the attention of politicians and the public. The article considers the directions of using elements of the digital economy as a driver of foreign economic activity. Some state programs on digitalization of national economies of the countries of the world are analyzed. Based on the results of the study, recommendations on digitalization of foreign economic activity of Uzbek enterprises have been developed.

Key words: *foreign economic activity, the fourth industrial revolution, digital platform, digital economy, digitalization.*

Концепция цифровой экономики приобрела популярность в последние годы и привлекла внимание политиков и общественности. В статье рассмотрены направления использования элементов цифровой экономики в качестве драйвера внешнеэкономической деятельности. Проанализированы некоторые государственные программы по цифровизации национальных экономик стран мира. На основе результатов исследования разработаны рекомендации по цифровизации внешнеэкономической деятельности предприятий Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: *внешнеэкономическая деятельность, четвертая промышленная революция, цифровая платформа, цифровая экономика, цифровизация.*

Raqamli iqtisodiyot kontseptsiyasi so'nggi yillarda mashhurlikka erishdi, siyosatchilar va jamoatchilik e'tiborini tortdi. Maqolada tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyat drayveri sifatida raqamli iqtisodiyot elementlaridan foydalanish yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqilyabdi. Dunyo mamlakatlari milliy iqtisodiyotini raqamlashtirish bo'yicha ba'zi davlat dasturlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijalari asosida O'zbekiston korxonalarining tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatini raqamlashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: *tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyat, to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobi, raqamli platforma, raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamlashtirish.*

The entry of the world community into the digital age brings with it the prospect of fundamental shifts in the mechanisms of functioning of all spheres of life and the entire complex of public relations both at the national and international levels. In the modern world, the greatest added value is created mainly in the sphere of the “new economy” and in those segments of the economy that have been digitized. In developed countries, the share of GDP generated in the digital economy

is rapidly increasing. The article considers only one particular aspect of this topic - the peculiarities of the development of foreign economic activity (FEA) in the conditions of digitalization. The vector is processes based on coordination, integration, unification of efforts in the field of development of information technologies and information and communication technologies in the field of foreign economic activity and capable of giving a powerful synergetic effect, reducing the risks of lagging behind the international process of digital transformation, in addition, reducing the risks of hacker attacks, cyber fraud. Given the rapid development of the digital economy, there are many definitions of it in the modern literature. The term was first used in 1995 by D.C. Proposed by Tapskott [1]. The dictionary of information society and the new economy refers to the digital economy, and the Oxford dictionary refers to the economy of electronic transactions through the Internet. The United Nations Commission on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) defines the digital economy as “the use of Internet-based digital technologies to produce goods and services” [2].

There are two main approaches in determining the role and place of digitalization in global industrial production. One of them interprets the current stage of the introduction of information technology achievements as evolutionary, the other as revolutionary. According to the second approach, the digital economy is the basis of the fourth industrial revolution, as the change in the underlying technology is clearly observed and there are signs of a change in the feasibility paradigm. The concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution matured under the influence of the German Industry 4.0 program and American developments in the field of the Internet of Things [3]. Its distinctive feature is the widespread introduction of cyber-physical systems into industrial production, the ability to independently manage and optimize it [4]. Analyzing the set of problems associated with this event, Klaus Schwab, founder and president of the World Economic Forum, said in his programmatic work: “The fourth industrial revolution will radically affect the global economy, it will be so comprehensive and multifaceted that will be” [5].

Along with different interpretations of the concept, the task of theoretically understanding the process of the impact of digital technologies on the world economy inevitably arises [6]. This effect is two kinds, like the emergence of any new complex technological wave: on the one hand, the economy is developing at a new level of interaction of all its elements, on the other hand, the old system of production and distribution of goods is being destroyed. It is no coincidence that digital technologies are described as “disruptive”.

The widespread introduction of digital technologies is one of the most important conditions for increasing the competitiveness of the national economy in all countries of the world [7]. It allows you to restructure the economy, reduce production costs and the cost of commercial operations, increase efficiency and reduce production time of goods, improve the quality and efficiency of services, including public services, introduction of new technologies and technological processes, access to services, education and allows you to create new opportunities for leisure activities. In addition, new jobs are being created. For example, the development of e-commerce has created 10 million jobs in China (1.3% of total jobs) [8] and the introduction of mobile applications has led to the employment of about 500,000 people in the United States over 5 years. The introduction of digital technologies has a direct impact on the implementation of international political relations. In particular, a direction of digital diplomacy has been formed, which includes the use of new technologies in solving foreign policy problems.

Scientific research makes different assessments of the economic benefits of digitization.

World Bank experts estimate that the contribution of the digital economy to the GDP of OECD countries is 6% [9]. Experts at Accenture Consulting estimate that the digital transformation will bring \$ 1.36 trillion to the top ten most developed countries in the world [10]. According to the European Commission, GDP growth will reach 415 billion euros per year as a result of the implementation of the Digital Single Market Strategy within the European Union [11]. The level of digitization of the national economies of the countries of the world varies greatly. Their achievements in this area can be assessed differently depending on the analysis criteria. Nevertheless, a group of leaders on the development of the digital economy has already been

formed. The World Economic Forum, according to a joint study by the School of Higher Management [12]. Johnson Cornell University and INSEAD Business School, Singapore have made the greatest strides in ICT implementation, and are among the top ten in Finland, Sweden, Norway, the US, the Netherlands, Switzerland, the UK, Luxembourg, and Japan. According to a study by the Spanish bank BBVA, the top ten includes Luxembourg, the UK, Hong Kong, the US, the Netherlands, Japan, Singapore, Norway, Finland and Sweden. [13].

The European Union has developed the International Digital Economy and Society Index (I-DESI), which is also used in the analysis of the level of digitization. It evaluates the performance of member states and the EU as a whole in comparison with the 15 “third countries” (non-integration partner countries). According to the study, Iceland is the world leader, followed by the Republic of Korea, Norway, New Zealand, Japan, the United States and Switzerland. In this study, Russia is ahead of China, Brazil, Turkey, and Mexico, but generally lags behind the European Union and significantly lags behind its leaders. According to more economists, more accurate results are provided by the Network Readiness Index (NRI), developed by experts from the World Economic Forum, which uses 3 groups of counters: economic and political conditions, regulatory framework and infrastructure; readiness of enterprises, government agencies and ordinary citizens to use ICT; Economic and social impact of ICT use [14].

The above-mentioned I-DESI index analysis takes into account the level of communication development, human capital, Internet use, digital technologies and the level of implementation of digital services to the population [15].

Development of the digital economy has become an urgent task for our country. For the first time, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018, Sh. Mirziyoyev officially proposed to implement the program “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” until 2030. Issues directly related to the digital economy have also been raised in the country's innovative development strategy. It is also set a task to double the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP by 2023. In this regard, the study of foreign experience in the development of the digital economy, the possibility of its application in our country is of practical interest.

According to UNCTAD, 102 digital strategies were developed in different countries around the world in 2012-2017, of which 30 were related to infrastructure development, 6 were aimed at promoting digital business, and 61 covered these two important areas [2]. Relevant policy documents of the largest international players - the United States, India, China and the European Union, with different approaches to shaping the state strategy for the development of the digital economy, have the greatest practical and research interests selected for this study. Their research allows us to cover countries with different economic structures and GDP growth rates. This competition allowed to assess the various tasks addressed by the strategic documents for use in the economic life of our country.

The main goal of the US Digital Economy Agenda is to create a conducive environment for American companies and to ensure that the United States plays a leading role in developing standards and regulations in a variety of formats. The U.S. Department of Commerce is responsible for its implementation. The coordination of the four structural units (National Institute of Standards and Technology, National Telecommunications and Information Agency, US Patent Office, and International Trade Office) involved in this process is managed by the Director of Digital Economy. His work is supported by the Digital Economy Advisory Board, established in March 2016, by experts from a number of American companies, civil society and academia.

The program involves working in four areas: free and open Internet; network trust and security; innovations and new technologies; introduction and professional skills.

Approved by Delhi in August 2014, “The Digital India” Program aims to transform the country into a “digital society and knowledge economy”. Defined tasks of the program: creating opportunities for citizens to use public services online; creating a digital infrastructure that every citizen should be able to use; “Preparing India for Future Knowledge”; High-speed Internet connection to “turn technology into a hub of change”.

Internet Plus's Action Plan until 2025, the concept of which was presented by Premier Li Keqiang of the State Council of the People's Republic of China in March 2015, and its content complements the China-made 2025 strategy released on July 4, 2015. The second is the long-term development plan of Chinese industry. Internet Plus aims to integrate the Internet, cloud computing, big data and the Internet of Things with modern manufacturing to develop industries, e-commerce and online banking and increase the international presence of Chinese Internet companies. The Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, the Ministry of Commerce, the National Development and Reform Commission and the Cyber Space Administration of China are involved in the implementation of this document. The Chairman of the State Council of the People's Republic of China personally supervises the process.

The digital economy in the EU first emerged in 2010, when the European Commission (EC) adopted the Digital Agenda for Europe, the first of seven initiatives under the Europe 2020 Strategy. Based on the experience gained in the implementation of this document, the "Single Digital Market Strategy for Europe" was approved in May 2015, covering many sections of the previous agenda. In addition, integration countries are implementing their own national programs.

On the basis of the studied materials it is possible to recommend the following directions on improvement of work of state bodies of the country on development of digital economy:

- harmonization of the regulatory framework with modern requirements;
- creating conditions for free movement of information;
- encouraging competition in the field of ICT, the use of digital technologies, the introduction of innovations;
- take additional measures to protect consumers when conducting transactions using the Internet;
- intensify efforts to increase the confidence of enterprises and citizens in the use of ICT, including increasing the level of network security and strengthening control over the use of personal data by companies;
- increase the effectiveness of copyright protection;
- copyright research in the digital economy;
- promoting business access to national innovation platforms and cloud services;
- appointment of digital technology specialists to work in trade missions of Uzbekistan in important countries to stimulate the export of high-tech products;
- expansion of public services through further development of the concept of e-government;
- improving e-government, including expanding public access to information from government agencies.

Eliminate unreasonable restrictions on the cross-border movement of digital content as part of the implementation of the digital agenda. An analysis of international trends in digital transformations shows that there is currently no ideal version of a national strategy that can be modeled on by other countries, including our own. Even the high level of globalization of the economy does not allow to combine these programs.

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UDK: 338.2

К АКТУАЛЬНЫМ ВОПРОСАМ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ

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В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы использования технологии кайдзен в целях совершенствования механизма управления персоналом на предприятиях лёгкой промышленности. В рамках исследования изучены вопросы по эффективному использованию технологии кайдзен. Автор изучил вопросы внедрения технологии кайдзен с учётом специфики исследуемой отрасли. В ходе исследования проведён анализ и даны рекомендации по результативному управлению персоналом с точки зрения учёта зарубежного опыта.

Ключевые слова. персонал, предприятие, кайдзен, управление, стимулирование персонала, зарубежный опыт, бережливое производство

Ushbu maqolada yengil sanoat korxonalarida xodimlarni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish maqsadida kayzen texnologiyasidan foydalanish masalalari tadqiqot qilingan. Tadqiqot doirasida kaizen texnologiyasidan samarali foydalanish masalalari o'rganilgan. Muallif o'rganilayotgan sohaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda kayzen texnologiyasini joriy etish masalalarini yoritgan. Tadqiqot jarayonida xorij tajribasini hisobga olgan holda xodimlarni samarali boshqarish bo'yicha tahlillar o'tkazilib, tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar:. kadrlar, korxonalar, kayzen, menejment, xodimlarni rag'batlantirish, xorijiy tajriba, tejamkor ishlab chiqarish

This article discusses the use of kaizen technology in order to improve the personnel management mechanism at light industry enterprises. Within the framework of the study, the questions of the effective use of kaizen technology were studied. The author studied the issues of introducing kaizen technology, taking into account the specifics of the industry under study. In the course of the study, an analysis was carried out and recommendations were given for effective personnel management from the point of view of taking into account foreign experience.

Keywords:. personnel, enterprise, kaizen, management, personnel stimulation, foreign experience, lean production.

На сегодняшний день вопросы совершенствования механизма управления персоналом на предприятиях лёгкой промышленности являются особенно актуальными. Как известно правильно организованное управление это ключ к успеху любого предприятия и предприятия лёгкой промышленности Ферганской области не являются исключением.

В своём исследовании мы бы хотели более подробно рассмотреть использование технологии кайдзен при управлении персоналом.

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Оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилиб,
2020 йил 6 августда № 1081 рақамли гувоҳнома олинди.

Босишга рухсат этилди: 10.11.2022 й.
Бичими: А4. Гарнитура Times New Roman.
Босма табоғи: 15,25. Адади 10 нусха. Буюртма № 3.
Баҳоси шартнома асосида.
«Alpha Print» босмаҳонасида чоп этилди.
Фарғона шаҳар, Фарғона кўчаси 86 -уй.
Лиц: №22-2891 21.11.2012 йил.